

MIDAS Open v202407

Release Notes, July 2024

Overview

This document summarises the recent improvements to the MIDAS Open dataset as part of this year's annual release.

As part of this new release, an agreement was reached to include rainfall data from rain gauges managed by three hydrological agencies in the MIDAS Open product, namely Environment Agency (EA), Scottish Environmental Protection Agency (SEPA) and Natural Resources Wales (NRW). This specifically refers to current open stations and closed stations where the last operating authority was either EA, SEPA or NRW.

The source IDs for these stations were added to the MIDAS Open dataset product and the valid data reporting roles was updated to include codes WAHRAIN (water authority hourly rainfall), WADRAIN (water authority daily rainfall) and WAMRAIN (water authority monthly rainfall).

The MIDAS Open dataset observations data will continue to be supplied in BADC-CSV format. The station metadata file for each dataset will now contain an "authority" column, indicating the latest operating authority for that station. If the station is part of the Met Office land network, but the rain gauge is owned by one of the hydrological agencies, this station will be listed as under the authority of the Met Office. An additional metadata tag for the station authority has also been added to the observations files and the station capability files.

Furthermore, the formatting of the values in the station change log files have been updated to remove trailing zeroes from non-numeric fields, for example instrument ID.

1. Inclusion of hydrological agency stations

Following the inclusion of observations data from rain gauges owned, or previously owned, by the Environment Agency, SEPA or Natural Resources Wales, the coverage of hourly rainfall data has increased from about 90% to 94% and daily rainfall from about 15% to about 58%. There is still a gap in the daily rainfall coverage due to the fact that a number of rain gauges recording daily rainfall were closed more than 25 years ago, prior to when the authority history metadata was stored. A separate decision will be made as to whether to include observations from these stations in a later version.

As well as including new stations, existing stations with rain gauges owned by one of the above hydrological agencies will have additional observations included for these particular gauges. These rain gauges will report under the WA domain roles:

- WAHRAIN – Water Authority hourly rainfall
- WADRAIN – Water Authority daily rainfall
- WAMRAIN – Water Authority monthly rainfall

All of these additional observations will be recorded in MIDAS Open in the same format as previous versions of the dataset, with the data stored in CSV files in region and station level directories. The capabilities for these stations/gauges will also be available in the capability CSV file.

2. Authority tag

This version of the MIDAS Open dataset will include one edit to the metadata, capability and observations files, namely the latest authority information for the station.

The station capability and observations files have an additional tag <authority> added to the metadata and the station metadata file has an additional authority column in the data table containing the latest owning authority for each station.

If the station is a UK station with a DCNN number, indicating that it is part of the Met Office land network, it will be listed as Met Office, even if the rain gauge is owned by a separate hydrological agency. Other stations which were last owned by one of the approved hydrological agencies will be listed as such.

3. Dataset coverage

Coverage statistics for MIDAS Open v202407:

Dataset	% Total MIDAS included (v202407)	% Total MIDAS excluded (v202407)	% Met Office stations (included)	% EA/SEPA/NRW stations (included)
Daily temperature	96%	4%	96%	0%
Daily rainfall	58%	42%	16%	42%
Hourly rainfall	94%	6%	92%	2%
Daily weather	96%	4%	96%	0%
Hourly weather	92%	8%	92%	0%
Soil temperature	98%	2%	98%	0%
Radiation	96%	4%	96%	0%
Mean wind	90%	10%	90%	0%

4. Station change log formatting

The previous version of the station change logs contained some fields, for example QC flags and instrument ID, output with trailing zeroes after a decimal point after they were incorrectly formatted as floats. In the latest version, all non-numeric values have been converted to strings to improve the readability of the logs.

See the table below for an example of some of the values that have updated for a particular change log record:

Version	Ob date	ID	Ob hour count	Version num	Min air temp Q	Rec st ind	Min air temp J
V202308 (previous)	2000-01-06	154.0	12.0	0.0	1.0	1012.0	NaN
V202407 (current)	2000-01-06	0154	12	0	1	1012	NA